

The Study on Skeleton Dense Quiet Pavement

Xueying Xu^a, Zuomin Wang^b, Weidong Cao^c, Xuejun Wang^d

^{a,d} Shanghai Volkswagen Corporation, Shanghai 201805, China

^b Institute of Acoustics, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, China

^c School of Civil Engineering, Shandong University,
Jinan 250061, China

ABSTRACT

Nowadays noise is becoming more and more disturbing in peoples daily life; particularly the traffic noise has been regarded as the most important noise source. At the speed of cars is more than $50 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, tire/road noise will indeed dominate traffic noise especially for light vehicles. In order to solve the problem of traffic noise, low noise pavements were widely used in many countries. Skeleton Dense Quiet Pavement (SDQP) is one kind of low noise pavements. On the basis of the fact that tire/road noise mainly arises from tread vibration, tire model and tire/road vibration model were used together in this paper, the correlation between rubber powder in pavement and tire vibration has also been studied. As for the SDQP, the percentage of rubber powder can directly affect the pavement stiffness and damping coefficient. The higher the percentage of rubber powder is, the less the stiffness will be and the more the damping coefficient will become. In order to testify the noise reducing effect of SDQP, the testing road of SDQP and a reference road of Asphalt Concrete (AC) were constructed. The results indicate that SDQP can decrease noise level by about 2 dB as compared with AC.

1 INTRODUCTION

Noise is today a serious environmental problem in people's daily life; particularly the traffic noise has been regarded as the most important noise source. From the aspect of noise sources, traffic noise mainly consists of engine noise, fan noise, intake (exhaust) noise, vehicle body vibration noise, tire/road noise and so on. At the speed is more than $50 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ [1], tire/road noise will indeed dominate the traffic noise especially for light vehicles. In order to solve the problem of traffic noise, low noise pavement is one of the most widely used measurements [2,3].

It has been accepted as low noise pavement [4,5], such as porous asphalt, rubber asphalt, Stone Mastic Asphalt (SMA), ultra-thin asphalt concrete and porous elastic road surface. Among which, traditional porous pavement (normally, porosity $\geq 15\%$) is most used, which can decrease the traffic noise level by 3-5dB (A) normally. However, it still has its own disadvantages that cannot be easily solved. Such as void clogging, raveling, etc. These demerits will directly weaken the noise reduction effect. Therefore, we have now turned to the study on non-porous or dense structure asphalt. The purpose of this study is to develop a new low noise pavement which is suitable for urban roads and streets, and is economical with excellent load performance and acoustical durability as well. In this paper, SDQP has been

^a Email address: xuxueying@csvw.com

^b Email address: zmwang@mail.tongji.edu.cn

^c Email address: cwd2001@sdu.edu.cn

^d Email address: wangxuejun@csvw.com

studied, with a combination of SMA (porosity is 3%~5%) and rubber powder. Studies on pavement parameters' effect on tire vibration form the correlation between rubber powder and tire vibration. By comparing differences between different kinds of pavements, the effect of rubber powder on dynamic modulus was analyzed, tire model and tire/road vibration model are also employed, and thereby the conclusion that SDQP with rubber powder (3%) is the best material to reduce tire vibration and noise has been reached.

2 DYNAMIC MODULES OF DIFFERENT PAVEMENTS

Three classes of asphalt mixtures were tested, including ordinary AC, SMA, SDQP with three different percentage composition of rubber powder (1%, 2%, 3%). The total mix was 5. Dynamic modulus and phase angle were measured with material testing system MTS810.

The measurement of complex dynamic modulus is widely used^[6,7] in the study of material property, with MTS the amplitude and phase angle difference of stress and strain can be measured individually.

$$E^* = E_1 + iE_2 \quad (1)$$

$$E^* = E_0 \cos \phi + iE_0 \sin \phi \quad (2)$$

Phase angle:

$$\phi = 360 fS \quad (3)$$

Where

f --load frequency, Hz;

S --time delay between stress and strain

Note that E_2 is also called dynamic modulus or storage modulus, E_1 is called Loss Modulus, which is the loss part of the energy in a deformation cycle, $i = \sqrt{-1}$.

Figure 1 shows the equipment of MTS810, the basic principle is, several sensors are set inside to get the stress, strain and displacement, all the measurement parameters can be displayed on the monitor of MTS810. Half-sine wave is employed; MTS is controlled by the load program, which is already set before.

Figure 1: MTS810 test system

The dimension of the sample is $\phi 10 \times 10$ cm, the temperature is 20°C , the maximum stress in axel is 0.7Mpa, the load frequency are 1Hz、10Hz、16Hz respectively, then the stress-strain curve can be calculated individually. Note that different load frequency can simulate different vehicle driving speed.

Table 1: dynamic and phase angle in different load frequency

Model	1Hz		10Hz		16Hz	
	Dynamic modulus(Mpa)	Phase angle(/°)	Dynamic modulus(Mpa)	Phase angle(/°)	Dynamic modulus(Mpa)	Phase angle (/°)
AC	952	14.30	1003	8.79	1030.7	5.63
SMA	813.2	14.30	956.6	10.54	1008.1	8.40
1%	805.3	16.09	946.3	12.30	981	11.25
2%	800.1	17.87	892.8	14.07	952.3	13.52
3%	787	21.44	887	19.21	932	16.87

Table 1 shows that dynamic modulus increased with the load frequency. AC has the maximum dynamic modulus, SMA ranks 2nd; Skeleton structure pavement with 3% rubber powder has the minimum dynamic modulus. Then the effect of rubber powder on dynamic modulus is obvious, pavement with more rubber powder has lower dynamic modulus, and big phase angle can also lead to more tire/road energy loss.

In short, Skeleton dense pavement with 3% rubber powder is better than other 4 kinds of pavements in tire vibration attenuation, due to the high damping coefficient of this pavement. The higher the percentage of rubber powder is, the less the stiffness will be and the more the damping coefficient will become.

3 TIRE/ROAD VIBRATION MODEL

In the past 30 years, many studies have proved that tire vibration is one of the most important sources of rolling noise^[8,9]. Unevenness of road play an important role in vibration excitation. In order to study the mechanism of noise reduction ability of different pavement, a two-degree tire/road model is proposed, as shown in Figure 2. Note that M_1, k_1, c_1 are the mass, stiffness and damping coefficient of tire; M_2, k_2, c_2 are the mass, stiffness and damping coefficient of pavement. Provided that different pavements have same surface property, in another word, they have the same unevenness and porosity, which can help to eliminate the effect of air pumping.

Figure 2: Tire/road interaction model.

As stated above, pavements with different rubber powder will lead to different stiffness and damping, which means tire vibration attenuation, will vary with the change of pavement. One measurement of tire vibration was made, in which c_2 was calculated respectively^[13]. SDQP with 3% has the maximum damping effect, then followed by 2%, 1% and SMA, AC has the minimum damping effect.

4 TIRE MODEL ANALYSIS

Generally speaking, tire model can be classified into two kind of models, one is low-frequency model (i.e., below 400 Hz), and the other is high-frequency model. In this paper, tire generation noise is mainly high frequency ^[10,11], therefore, a simplified high-frequency tire model is employed ^[12]. In this model, tire is simplified as a pre-tensioned orthotropic Kirchhoff's plate, tread and tire side are both considered. Figure 3 is the schematic illustration of such a model, the bending behavior of tire surface is not considered, but the periodicity of the tire in rolling direction, that is to say the boundary condition of tire's two ends is continuous. Meanwhile, air pressure and the stiffness of sidewall are also included, which form the spring foundation of the plate. Besides, the properties such as bending stiffness, spring stiffness and tension are all in the model.

Differential equation of the plate in vertical direction:

$$T_0 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial y^2} \right) + B_x \frac{\partial^4 \xi}{\partial x^4} + 2B_{xy} \frac{\partial^4 \xi}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + B_y \frac{\partial^4 \xi}{\partial y^4} - m'' \omega^2 \xi + s \xi = F_0'' \quad (4)$$

Figure 3 One layer plate model.

T_0 is the tension of the plate due to air in the tire, B_x , B_y are the bending stiffness in circular and lateral, B_{xy} is the square root of product of B_x and B_y . ξ is the displacement of plate in vertical direction, it is also the radial displacement of the tread. s is the spring stiffness of plate, m'' is the section mass, F_0'' is the outside force on the section. Since the loss factor of the material, B_x , B_y , B_{xy} , T_0 and s are complex, the imagine part indicates the damping effect.

For the simple supporte plate model, the eigenfunction in x direction :

$$\Phi_n = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi n}{l_x} x\right) n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (5)$$

Displacement and vibration in two ends are complete the same in x direction.

For lateral, simple supported at sidewall :

$$\psi_m = \sin\left(\frac{\pi m}{l_y} y\right) m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M \quad (6)$$

then, displacement ξ can be written:

$$\xi(x, y, \omega) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=0}^N \xi_{m,n} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi n}{l_x} x\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi m}{l_y} y\right) \quad (7)$$

$$\xi_{m,n}(x, y, \omega) = \Lambda(\omega) \Phi_n(x) \Psi_m(y) \quad (8)$$

F_0'' can be written:

$$F_0''(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=0}^N B_{m,n} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi n}{l_x} x\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi m}{l_y} y\right) \quad (9)$$

Then $B_{m,n}$:

$$B_{m,n} = \frac{\sin\left(\frac{2\pi n d_x}{l_x}\right) \left[\cos\left(\frac{(y_0 - d_y)m\pi}{l_y}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{(y_0 + d_y)m\pi}{l_y}\right) \right]}{n\pi d_x m\pi d_y} \quad (10)$$

Hier (x_0, y_0) is the middle of the thin plate, $2d_x, 2d_y$ are the length and width of the excite area (rectangular).

Equation (7), (9) and (10) can be substituted to equation(4):

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{m,n} \left[-T_0(k_x^2 + k_y^2) + B_x k_x^4 + 2B_{xy} k_x^2 k_y^2 + B_y k_y^4 - m'' \omega^2 + s \right] \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=0}^N \cos(k_x x) \sin(k_y y) \\ = B_{m,n} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=0}^N \cos(k_x x) \sin(k_y y) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Where $k_x = \frac{2\pi n}{l_x}, k_y = \frac{\pi m}{l_y}$.

Equation (11) can be multiplied by $\cos(k_x x) \sin(k_y y)$, and then integrated in the whole plate by x and y, then:

$$\xi_{m,n} = \frac{B_{m,n}}{A_{m,n}} \quad (12)$$

$$A_{m,n} = T_0(-k_x^2 - k_y^2) + B_x k_x^4 + 2B_x B_y k_x^2 k_y^2 + B_y k_y^4 - m'' \omega^2 + s \quad (13)$$

For a certain frequency ω :

$$\xi_\omega = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{B_{m,n} \cos(k_x x) \sin(k_y y)}{A_{m,n}} \quad (14)$$

Provided in the area $(2d_x, 2d_y)$, the excite force is equal and uniformly distributed, then in the excite area:

$$F_0'' = F / 4d_x d_y$$

Radial vibration response can be written:

$$\frac{V}{F} = \frac{i\omega \xi}{F} = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=0}^N i\omega \frac{B_{m,n} \cos(k_x x) \sin(k_y y)}{A_{m,n}} \quad (15)$$

Figure 4: vibration response in the middle of excite area

The measurement results of dynamic modulus from MTS can be substituted to equation (15), then the vibration velocity response V/F can be calculated, the results of AC and skeleton dense pavement with 3% rubber powder in the frequency range (400~1400Hz) were shown in Figure 4, this frequency range is of great importance for the tire noise emission. Radial vibration velocity of tire on AC pavement is quite faster than that on 3%, especially at 1100Hz, $20\lg(V_{AC}/V_{3\%}) \approx 1.7\text{dB}$. This can explain why the 3% has better noise reduction ability than AC. Calculations of the response of the tire to an external excitation show relatively good agreement with measurements on the testing roads ^[13]; the results indicate that SDQP can decrease noise level by about 2 dB as compared with AC.

5 SUMMARY

As for the SDQP, the percentage of rubber powder can directly affect the pavement's stiffness and damping coefficient. The higher the percentage of rubber powder is, the less the stiffness will be and the more the damping coefficient will become. In order to ensure the structure strength of the pavement, the percentage of rubber powder should be no more than 3%. Compared with other different pavements' effect on tire vibration attenuation, the conclusion can be drawn that the SDQP with 3% rubber powder has the best performance in noise reduction and vibration attenuation.

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7 REFERENCES

- [1] D. Stanners and P. Bourdeau (editors), "1995 Europe's Environment," Copenhagen: European Environment Agency, (1995).
- [2] K. Attenborough, S. I. Hayek and J. M. Lawther, "Propagation of sound above a porous half-space," *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, **68**, 1493-1501 (1980).
- [3] M. C. Berengier, M. R. Stinson, G. A. Daigle and J. F. Hamet, "Porous road pavement: Acoustical characterization and propagation effects," *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, **101** (1), 155-162 (1977).
- [4] Kenneth W., Fults, "QUIET PAVEMENT SYSTEMS," FHWA/AASHTO INTERNATIONAL TECHNOLOGY SCAN, Draft Executive Summary Report, 2004.

- [5] Luc Goubert, Jan Hooghwerff and Peter The, "Two-layer porous asphalt: an international survey in the frame of the Noise Innovation Programme (IPG)," The 2005 Congress Exposition on Noise Control Engineering, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2005.
- [6] *Dynamic Property and Dynamic Parameter of Asphalt Surface Material*, edited by Wang Xudong, Sha Aimin and Xu Zhihong (People's transportation Publishing house, Beijing, 2002).
- [7] *Pavement Performance of Asphalt and Asphalt Mixture*, edited by Shen Jin'an (People's transportation Publishing house, Beijing, 2001).
- [8] M.Heckl, "Tyre Noise Generation," *Wear*, **113**,157-170 (1986).
- [9] Keijiro Iwao and IchiroYamazaki, "A studyon the mechanism of tire/road noise," *JSAE Review*, **17**,1382144 (1996).
- [10] Rimondi.G, "Tire Contribution in the Automobile Noise Reduction," *Tire Science and Technology*, **23**(3), 189-208 (1995).
- [11] Doan,V.Q.,Brackin,D.,Nishihata.S.and Sauerzapf.J, "Investigation into the Influence of Construction on Coast-by Noise," *Tire Science and Technology*, **23**(2), 96-115 (1995).
- [12] W. Kropp, "Structural-borne sound on a smooth tyre," *Applied Acoustics*, **26**, 181-192 (1989).
- [13] Xueying Xu, "The Study on Skeleton Dense Quiet Pavement,"Doctor Thesis of Tongji University,2007